

ISic1260

I.Sicily inscription 1260

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

breccia (pietra rossa di Taormina)

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico, inventory 2

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140748

1. Γάιος Κλαύδιος
2. Μαάρκου υἱὸς Μαάρκελλος
3. Γ
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492866

EDCS 39101628

PHI 140748

Bibliography

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